

11-16 AUGUST 2019

22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

A Plate Model for Damage Tolerance Prediction and Design for Multi-Axial Loading

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Introduction

- Impact damage can reduce Compression After Impact (CAI) strength by over 80% [1].
- Laminates must be tolerant to such damage.
- Design to increase load at which damage propagates is critical to reducing aircraft weight.

Plate Model Theory

- Multi-axial model to evaluate full 2D energy available to cause crack growth [2].
- Assume buckling occurs at certain level $\{\varepsilon^C\}$ calculated by buckling software VICONOPT [3].
- SERR obtained via the energy difference in the system from before and after elliptical growth of the post-buckle and concurrent delamination.
- Elliptical growth assumed to occur.
- Mode I energy with zero post-buckled stiffness is assumed.

[2] Choudhry RS, Rhead AT, Nielsen MW, Butler R. A plate model for compressive strength prediction of delaminated composites. *Compos Struct* 2019;210:509–17.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2018.11.066>

[3] Williams FW, Kennedy D, Anderson MS, Butler R. VICONOPT - Program for exact vibration and buckling analysis or design of prismatic plate assemblies. *AIAA J* 1991;29(11):1927–1928.

Plate Model Theory

Bending energy U'_B assumed to accumulate similar to a strut with zero-post buckled stiffness. A is the area of the delamination. A_{sl} is the sublaminates stiffness matrix.

$$\int_0^A U'_B dA = \int_0^A (\{\varepsilon^c\}^T [A_{sl}] (\{\varepsilon\} - \{\varepsilon^c\})) dA$$

Membrane energy is released from the small regions either side of the buckle which will form the new buckle with growth.

$$\int_0^A U_M^* dA = \int_0^A (U_M - U'_B) dA = \frac{\pi ab}{2} (\{\varepsilon\}^T [A_{sl}] \{\varepsilon\} - \{\varepsilon^c\}^T [A_{sl}] \{\varepsilon^c\})$$

ΔU evaluates change of energy in these regions with $\Delta A = \text{SERR}$. Set against a Mode I fracture criterion for conservatism + 2 crack fronts.

$$\frac{dU}{dA} = \frac{G_{IC}}{2}$$

Plate Model Equation

When $G = G_{IC}$, $\{\varepsilon\} = \{\varepsilon_{th}\}$ and $F = F_{th}$. Solving for $\varepsilon_{x,th}$ gives:

$$\varepsilon_{x,th} = \varepsilon_x^C \left(\sqrt{4 + \frac{G_{IC}}{u_T}} - 1 \right)$$

Where $u_T = A_{11sl}(\varepsilon_x^C)^2 + 2A_{12sl}\varepsilon_x^C\varepsilon_y^C + A_{22sl}(\varepsilon_y^C)^2$ for stiffness and strains in principal directions. ε_x^C is obtained from VICONOPT. For full derivation and experimental results see [2].

CAI predictions

Model predictions correlate well with uni-axial CAI tests with artificial delaminations.

Conservative and within 12% for all balanced laminates.

Potential for use in initial design optimisation.

Damage Tolerant Design

Therefore $\{\varepsilon^C\}$ is unknown and we must assume worst case damage and a worst case depth to cause a worst case $\{\varepsilon_{th}\}$.

Plate Model equation gives:

Subbing in Plate Model Equation creates a threshold prediction to independent of ε^C :

$$\varepsilon_{x,th,min} \sqrt{T_{sl}} = \sqrt{\frac{3G_{IC}}{4Q_{sl}^*}} \propto \text{CAI Strain}$$

$$\varepsilon_{x,th,min} = \sqrt{\frac{3G_{IC}}{4Q_{sl}^* T_{sl}}}$$

where $Q_{sl}^* = Q_{11,sl} - 2\nu_L Q_{12,sl} + \nu_L^2 Q_{22,sl}$ and ν_L is the laminate Poisson's ratio (or y to -x strain).*

*Current format is for principal loading directions

Damage Tolerant Design

Apply to any general loading state and produce design up to critical depth, T_{sl} , (10-20%) below which delamination does not open.

Parameter Study with all Standard Angle (SA) proportions: $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° optimal for SA surface plies when uni-axial loading and $\nu_L = 0.32$.

Damage Tolerant Design

Non-Standard angles can produce greater CAI performance.

$$\epsilon_y = -\nu_L \epsilon_x$$

Conclusions

- Current Plate model is conservative and accurate to 12% for balanced sub-laminates.
- Model can be adapted to cope with unknown damage morphology.
- Worst case model is suitable for use in damage tolerant design optimisation.
- Shows potential of near surface non-standard angles.
- Improve CAI model to capture all sublaminates coupling behaviour.

Acknowledgements

Research supported by EPSRC (EP/N024354/1) funding for the ADAPT project with GKN/Airbus/Chomarar/NCC.

